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THE IMPACT OF VITAMIN D DEFICIENCY ON THE PREVALENCE OF DENTAL PATHOLOGY

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ANNOTATION

The role of vitamin D is explained by its numerous beneficial effects on systemic health. This publication examines the influence of vitamin D deficiency and the use of vitamin D on dental pathology and preventive dentistry. Vitamin D is a fat-soluble vitamin that exists in several forms, including vitamin D2 (ergocalciferol), primarily found in plant-based foods and mushrooms, and vitamin D3 (cholecalciferol or calcidiol), physiologically present in humans. Vitamin D3 participates in bone metabolism and numerous physiological processes in the body. Approximately 80–90% of vitamin D in humans is synthesized in the skin under the influence of ultraviolet sunlight, while smaller amounts are obtained through dietary intake such as fatty fish and egg yolk. Vitamin D2 from plant sources is absorbed in considerably lower quantities. Following hydroxylation, vitamin D3 is converted into its storage form, calcidiol, compensating for the absence of endogenous vitamin D synthesis in conditions of insufficient sun exposure. Depending on hydroxylation processes, vitamin D may exist in active or inactive forms, as well as in precursor states.

Keywords: vitamin D deficiency, osseointegration, dental implants, regeneration, bone metabolism, mineral imbalance, periodontitis, dental caries, implant osseointegration.

Introduction. Vitamin D synthesis in the human body involves a steroid hormone produced in the skin under sufficient sunlight exposure (wavelengths 290–315 nm). Under ultraviolet B (UV-B) radiation, 7-dehydrocholesterol (7-DHC) is converted into previtamin D₃, which is subsequently transformed into vitamin D₃. A transport protein carries vitamin D₃ to the liver, where enzymatic hydroxylation results in the formation of 25-hydroxyvitamin D₃ [25(OH)D₃], also known as calcidiol [16]. From the liver, 25(OH)D₃ is transported to the kidneys, where it is converted into the metabolically active form 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D₃ (calcitriol). In addition to the kidneys, several tissues possess local 1- α -hydroxylase activity, including bone tissue, placenta, prostate gland, keratinocytes, macrophages, T lymphocytes, dendritic cells, certain cancer cells, and parathyroid glands [7]. Excessive sun exposure, however, can convert previtamin D₃ and vitamin D₃ into inactive photoproducts, thereby preventing vitamin D overproduction in the skin.

The main causes of impaired cutaneous synthesis of vitamin D₃ and reduced serum vitamin D levels include prolonged indoor stay, use of sunscreens and cosmetic products that block ultraviolet radiation, limited sun exposure, dark skin pigmentation, advanced age, prolonged bed rest, and clothing that covers most of the body [8]. These factors determine the need for an optimal sun exposure regimen sufficient to ensure adequate vitamin D₃ synthesis while avoiding sunburn. Another important issue is that only a limited number of food products contain significant amounts of vitamin D, including fatty marine fish, fish oil, eggs, edible mushrooms, dairy products, and cheese. Dietary intake alone is generally insufficient to compensate for reduced ultraviolet exposure during winter months. On average, 15–20 minutes of direct sunlight exposure is considered sufficient for synthesis of approximately 10,000 international units (IU) of vitamin D₃ [31]. Individuals with darker skin pigmentation usually require less vitamin D₃ supplementation than lightly pigmented individuals [20].

Vitamin D plays a crucial role in calcium and phosphate homeostasis, mineral balance, and regulation of bone metabolism [4]. The active form of vitamin D₃, synthesized predominantly in the kidneys under conditions of reduced serum

phosphate and parathyroid hormone activity, stimulates intestinal absorption of calcium and phosphates while decreasing their urinary excretion. In addition, calcitriol contributes to bone mineralization through multiple mechanisms. Data regarding the effects of vitamin D on osteoclasts remain controversial [10]. Some studies report inhibitory effects on osteoclast development [39], whereas others demonstrate stimulatory effects [11]. Vitamin D increases production of receptor activator of nuclear factor kappa-B ligand (RANKL) and expression of osteocalcin mRNA in osteoblasts, positively influencing osteoclast formation and activation [18]. However, the vitamin D receptor (VDR), together with vitamin D, suppresses RANKL activity. Consequently, osteoclast formation and bone resorption are inhibited [1]. Furthermore, vitamin D decreases expression of NFATc1 and increases interferon- β (IFN- β) expression, preventing osteoclastogenesis and differentiation [9]. Nevertheless, calcidiol, the storage form of vitamin D (25-hydroxyvitamin D), may stimulate osteoclast differentiation [24].

Vitamin D deficiency. Vitamin D deficiency is usually caused by insufficient synthesis of vitamin D in the body due to inadequate sun exposure and/or age-related decline in the synthetic capacity of the skin. Severe chronic vitamin D deficiency results in bone demineralization with clinical manifestations of rickets in children and osteomalacia in adults [6]. Low vitamin D concentrations reduce intestinal absorption of calcium and phosphate derived from food [38], which subsequently increases circulating levels of parathyroid hormone (PTH) [12].

Secondary hyperparathyroidism increases serum calcium concentrations to suboptimal levels and leads to bone demineralization through mobilization of calcium from skeletal tissues caused by enhanced osteoclast activity and increased renal phosphate excretion [26]. Bone density consequently decreases, contributing to osteopenia and osteoporosis. Another consequence of secondary hyperparathyroidism is phosphaturia, which may develop despite normal or low serum phosphate levels. This results in disruption of the phosphate-calcium balance and creates a deficiency in skeletal mineralization [37].

In early childhood, low skeletal mineralization associated with vitamin D deficiency may lead to various skeletal deformities commonly recognized as rickets [5]. In adult patients with large bone mass and closed epiphyseal plates, skeletal deformities are usually absent; however, defective mineralization develops in the form of osteomalacia, characterized by accumulation of uncalcified bone matrix, reduced bone density, muscular weakness, and bone pain [14,36]. Catabolic metabolic disturbances related to vitamin D deficiency may also result in osteoporotic fractures and impaired periodontal healing [33].

Role of vitamin D deficiency in periodontal pathology. A correlation has been demonstrated between severity of periodontitis and low serum concentrations of 25(OH)-vitamin D, suggesting an association between vitamin D deficiency and both the pathogenesis and progression of periodontal disease [19,34]. However, the precise effects of hypovitaminosis D on immune cells, periodontal tissues, and periodontal pathogens remain incompletely understood [3]. Experimental studies in mice with periodontitis and diabetes demonstrated increased levels of gingival epithelial proteins VDR and PTPN2, whereas reduced concentrations of 25-hydroxyvitamin D were associated with decreased VDR expression. Production of nuclear transcription factor NF- κ B, which regulates key mechanisms of innate and adaptive immune responses, is also associated with levels of 25-hydroxyvitamin D3. In mice with isolated periodontitis, adequate concentrations of 25-hydroxyvitamin D3 reduced expression of phosphorylated Janus kinase-1 (pJAK1), which regulates immunocytokine processes [9].

Experimental investigations have shown that vitamin D exerts dose-dependent inhibitory and antibacterial effects on periodontopathogenic and cariogenic microorganisms, including *Porphyromonas gingivalis*, *Fusobacterium nucleatum*, *Aggregatibacter actinomycetemcomitans*, *Streptococcus moorei*, and *Streptococcus mutans*. Vitamin D suppresses the growth of *P. gingivalis* by significantly reducing expression of virulence factor genes (VFGs), including *fimA*, *hagA*, *hagB*, *rgpA*, and *rgpB*, which are involved in bacterial colonization, evasion of host defense

mechanisms, tissue destruction, and nutrient acquisition. Furthermore, vitamin D dose-dependently inhibits activation of NF- κ B in *P. gingivalis* [14].

After binding to the vitamin D receptor (VDR), vitamin D influences the immune system by enhancing expression of β -defensin 4A (DEFB4A) and cathelicidin [30]. Vitamin D also suppresses T-lymphocyte activity through reduction of proliferation and decreased production of IL-2 and IFN- γ [17]. Deficiency of vitamin D may therefore reduce these protective effects. It has additionally been demonstrated that vitamin D lowers concentrations of inflammatory cytokines such as IL-8 and CCL2 within periodontal secretions [3]. In human periodontal fibroblasts, vitamin D supplementation increases expression of osteopontin and osteocalcin mRNA while enhancing alkaline phosphatase activity, resulting in reduced inflammation and tissue degradation [28].

Vitamin D in prevention of dental caries. Since the beginning of the twentieth century, numerous studies have investigated associations between vitamin D and dental caries. Early twentieth-century investigations demonstrated that vitamin D supplementation reduced the risk of dental caries by approximately 47%. Replacement of vitamin D₂ with vitamin D₃ and endogenous synthesis of vitamin D₃ under ultraviolet radiation did not significantly alter the preventive effect [40]. Children exposed to full-spectrum sunlight demonstrated significantly lower DMFS scores and lower incidence of caries in primary teeth compared with children exposed only to standard indoor lighting over a six-year period [35]. Similar results were obtained in hamster models after ultraviolet irradiation [29].

The anti-cariogenic effects of ultraviolet exposure may therefore be associated with stimulation of endogenous vitamin D synthesis. Contemporary studies evaluating serum 25(OH)-vitamin D levels have shown that children with higher serum concentrations experience significantly fewer complications during dental anesthesia and treatment compared with children with lower vitamin D levels [23]. Marked reductions in caries prevalence have been observed in children with serum 25(OH)-vitamin D concentrations exceeding 50 nmol/L [31]. Comparable findings were reported by Carvalho Silva et al., whereas serum concentrations below 75

nmol/L were associated with increased risk of permanent dentition caries in children [25]. In addition to the previously described protective effect, higher serum concentrations of 25(OH)-vitamin D were associated with significantly greater mineralization of permanent tooth roots [19].

When does vitamin D deficiency occur? Serum 25(OH)D concentration (1 ng/mL = 2.5 nmol/L) is considered the principal laboratory marker for assessing vitamin D status. Serum concentrations below 25 nmol/L are classified as pathological because they are associated with development of rickets [20]. At present, no universally accepted standards for serum vitamin D concentrations exist [4,21]. According to the United States Institute of Medicine (IOM), 20–100% of elderly men and women in the United States, Canada, and Europe experience vitamin D deficiency [32]. Both children and adults are at risk for vitamin D insufficiency. Postmenopausal women and elderly individuals particularly frequently exhibit inadequate serum vitamin D levels [18]. Approximately 80% of young adults from nine European countries, including Germany, demonstrated serum 25(OH)-vitamin D levels below optimal values; 27% had deficiency (27.5–49.9 nmol/L), and 15% had severe deficiency (<27.5 nmol/L) [7]. These findings indicate a high probability of vitamin D deficiency or insufficient vitamin D intake regardless of age.

Vitamin D and implant osseointegration. The beneficial effects of vitamin D on bone metabolism and mineral balance may also be utilized in dental practice. Based on analogous experimental studies in animals, it may be assumed that patients with adequate vitamin D levels can achieve more successful therapy and improved osseointegration of dental implants compared with patients affected by vitamin D deficiency [9]. Experimental investigations demonstrated that in animals with systemic conditions such as chronic kidney disease, diabetes mellitus, or osteoporosis, vitamin D administration improved osseointegration of dental implants [3,22,29]. This effect, however, was observed primarily in the presence of vitamin D deficiency [25]. Mechanisms identified in experimental animal studies may also be applicable to humans. Several reports associate early implant loss with insufficient serum vitamin D levels [14,39].

Clinical effects of vitamin D. In addition to its beneficial influence on bone health, vitamin D supplementation has been associated with multiple extraskeletal positive effects [21]. Adequate vitamin D intake is linked to reduced mortality from cancer, respiratory infections, and type 1 diabetes, as well as improved mood, mental health, quality of life, physical performance, and reduction of oxidative stress [25]. Although the positive role of vitamin D replacement therapy in patients with confirmed deficiency is widely accepted, opinions remain controversial regarding supplementation among healthy individuals. Many investigators do not recommend universal screening because of potential adverse effects associated with excessive doses or unnecessary treatment [11]. Instead, targeted preventive approaches are considered more rational [17,32].

The Institute of Medicine recommends a baseline intake of 400 international units (IU) of vitamin D daily for all population groups. A daily dose of 600 IU is recommended for children after the first year of life, as well as for adolescents and adults up to 70 years of age. Individuals older than 71 years and people with increased skin pigmentation are advised to consume 800 IU daily. The maximal recommended intake is 1000 IU daily for infants and 4000 IU daily for children aged 9 years and older, and these values should not be exceeded under any circumstances [14,25]. Excessive supplementation has been associated with reduced bone density [19]. In preventive and therapeutic management of vitamin D deficiency, vitamin D₃ (cholecalciferol) is preferred over vitamin D₂ because it increases serum 25(OH)-vitamin D concentrations more effectively [27]. Moreover, it has been proposed that vitamin D may exert stronger extraskeletal effects in individuals with vitamin D deficiency compared with individuals who already have optimal serum levels [33]. Experimental studies in animals also demonstrated that vitamin D supplementation reduced fracture risk in elderly patients receiving inpatient or outpatient treatment [29]. In individuals without specific risk factors for deficiency, routine vitamin D supplementation for osteoporosis prevention may be unnecessary [1]. Supplementation does not appear to improve bone density or decrease fracture risk in healthy individuals [6].

Regarding the effect of supplementation on the success of dental implant osseointegration, experimental animal studies demonstrated improved osseointegration in animals with pathological disturbances of bone metabolism following vitamin D administration [13,24]. Vitamin D may also be applied locally by coating implant surfaces. Various implant surface modification strategies using vitamin D have been proposed. However, several experimental studies in animals failed to demonstrate significant enhancement of osseointegration after vitamin D application [16,27,40].

In summary, available evidence suggests that vitamin D plays an important role in the pathogenesis of maxillofacial diseases and in reparative regeneration following medical interventions. Because existing data regarding the influence of vitamin D on inflammatory processes and tissue repair remain partly contradictory, continued investigation in this field is necessary.

Conclusion. Analysis of contemporary literature demonstrates that serum vitamin D concentration plays a significant role in dental practice and may be useful in treatment planning, prognosis assessment, optimization of therapy, and evaluation of treatment success. Vitamin D status is currently considered a potential etiological factor in various systemic diseases and oral pathologies. To prevent vitamin D deficiency and associated diseases, patients at increased risk should undergo assessment of vitamin D status, followed by preventive supplementation when indicated, especially during periods of reduced sunlight exposure. Positive clinical effects of vitamin D supplementation have been observed in patients with dementia, chronic kidney disease, cancer, depression, alopecia, tooth loss, periodontitis, and osteoporosis, as well as in elderly individuals, people with increased skin pigmentation, individuals with unbalanced nutrition or limited sun exposure, pregnant and lactating women, and children under two years of age. The positive impact of vitamin D supplementation on dental treatment outcomes also supports its перспективность in contemporary dental practice.

References

1. A. Alkhenizan, A. Mahmoud, A. Hussain et al. The relationship between 25(OH)D levels (Vitamin D) and bone mineral density (BMD) in a Saudi population in a community-based setting. *PLoS One*. 2017;12.
2. L. Allard, N. Demoncheaux, I. Machuca-Gayet et al. Biphasic effects of vitamin D and FGF23 on human osteoclast biology. *Calcified Tissue International*. 2015;97(1):69–79.
3. R.J. Allison, A. Farooq, A. Cherif et al. Why don't serum vitamin D concentrations associate with BMD by DXA? A case of being “bound” to the wrong assay? Implications for vitamin D screening. *British Journal of Sports Medicine*. 2018;52:522–526.
4. A. Aloia, M. Mikhail, R. Dhaliwal et al. Free 25(OH)D and the vitamin D paradox in African Americans. *Journal of Clinical Endocrinology & Metabolism*. 2015;100:3356–3363.
5. D. Bellavia, V. Costa, A. De Luca et al. Vitamin D level between calcium-phosphorus homeostasis and immune system: new perspective in osteoporosis. *Current Osteoporosis Reports*. 2016:1–12.
6. R. Bouillon Comparative analysis of nutritional guidelines for vitamin D. *Nature Reviews Endocrinology*.
7. A.V. Prabhu, W. Luu, L.J. Sharpe et al. Cholesterol-mediated degradation of 7-dehydrocholesterol reductase switches the balance from cholesterol to vitamin D synthesis. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*. 2016;291(16):8363–8373.
8. K.D. Cashman, M. Kiely Recommended dietary intakes for vitamin D: where do they come from, what do they achieve and how can we meet them? *Journal of Human Nutrition and Dietetics*. 2014;27(5):434–442.
9. S. Christakos, P. Dhawan, A. Verstuyf et al. Vitamin D: metabolism, molecular mechanism of action, and pleiotropic effects. *Physiological Reviews*. 2016;96(1):365–408.

- 10.D.D. Bikle Vitamin D: Production, Metabolism and Mechanisms of Action. Updated December 31, 2021.
- 11.G. De Pascale, S.A. Quraishi Vitamin D status in critically ill patients: the evidence is now bioavailable! *Critical Care*. 2014;18:449.
- 12.A. Gil, J. Plaza-Diaz, D. Mesa Vitamin D: Classic and Novel Actions. *Annals of Nutrition and Metabolism*. 2018;72(2):87–95.
- 13.A. Giustina et al. Controversies in Vitamin D: A Statement from the Third International Conference. *JBMR Plus*. 2020;4:e10417.